

Physico-Chemical Studies of Catechins and Epicatechins

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The physico-chemical properties of (-)-epicatechin, (+)-catechin have been found to be at variance from those reported in literature, and have been corrected after confirmation, by elemental analysis, TGA etc. A quasiracemate ($C_{15}H_{14}O_6 \cdot 3H_2O$) of (-)-epicatechin and (+)-catechin (1 : 1) has also been isolated and characterised.

In India more than one million tons of heartwood of *Acacia catechu* (wild), is processed annually for obtaining pale catechu (*Katha*) and cutch. And yet it is a bit strange that (-)-epicatechin (for which *Acacia catechu* wild is the richest source) is not available in quantities enough to conduct clinical trials. Obviously, this prompted us to conduct a thorough search of the literature for a good preparative method, but with little success. The patent of Karnik and Sharma¹ describes a method, which gives a product containing not more than 85% purity with respect to catechins. Rather, we came across a large number of conflicting and contradictory reports.

In this paper we wish to rationalise the transformations of epicatechins and catechins along with their physical characteristics. The physical characteristics for the isomeric catechins given in the literature^{2,3} (Table 1), have been found to be at variance from our study as confirmed by both elemental and thermogravimetric analysis of (-)-epicatechin, (+)-catechin and (\pm)-catechin. This study has further helped in developing for the first time the commercial production methods for these three isomeric products and have been applied for patents⁴.

Results and Discussion

Thermogravimetric and elemental analysis of catechins ($C_{15}H_{14}O_6 \cdot xH_2O$): (-)-Epicatechin (2R, 3R) *cis* form, after crystallisation from water and drying in air at room temperature or in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride, did not contain any water of crystallisation ($x=0$) and melts at 242-44°. Thermogravimetric measurements (Fig. 1) confirmed this. (-)-Epicatechin is extremely stable and the first fragmentation starts only above 300°. In amber coloured and closed containers it did not change colour or physical characteristics for over 3 years.

(+)-Catechin (2R, 3S) *trans* form, when freshly crystallised and air dried at room temperature is a

tetrahydrate and melts at 97°. The tetrahydrate ($x=4$) on drying over fused calcium chloride loses two of its water molecules (2-5 days, depending

Fig. 1. Thermogram of (-)-epicatechin O. *Cis* (2R, 3R) form.

upon environmental temperature) and a stable dihydrate ($x=2$) is obtained with a melting point of 174-76°. Drying at 80-85° produces anhydrous (+)-catechin ($x=0$) which melts at 209-10°. Slow heating during the determination of melting points also dehydrates it and melts at 209-10°. The TGA (Fig. 2) further confirms that the dehydration of dihydrate of (+)-catechin starts around 60° and completes at 200°. The residual product does not decompose earlier than 260°, which is far above its melting point. Again, the dihydrate has a tendency to gain water and to change to tetrahydrate under high humidity condition (RH above 50%).

Fig. 2. Thermogram of (+)-catechin \blacktriangle . *Trans* (2R, 3S) form.

(\pm)-Catechin, the racemate, crystallises as a very stable trihydrate ($x=3$), which does not show any tendency to lose the water of crystallisation and melts at 210-12°. Its mixed melting point with (+)-catechin is 144-48°. The TGA (Fig. 3) indicates that the dehydration did not start before 150° and followed a continuous loss ($-3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) upto 375°. The residue is stable upto 575°.

(\pm)-Catechin (racemate of *trans* form) is the chief constituent (30-60%) along with tannins, of the trade product-pale catechu (*Katha*), which is the

Fig. 3. Thermogram of (\pm)-catechin \bullet .

conversion product of ($-$)-epicatechin. The information about the transformation of ($-$)-epicatechin to (\pm)-catechin is quite sketchy and the mechanism is not fully understood. Along with fresh studies we have repeated some of the literature reports and concluded that all the isomeric catechins are very prone to transformations and polymerisation under alkaline conditions. Epicatechins (with *cis* configuration) have a much lower life time than the catechins (with *trans* configuration). Pedersen *et al.*⁵, even with fast speed esr studies, failed to note any special characteristics for ($-$)-epicatechin (2R, 3R form). The esr spectra of oxygen saturated alkaline solutions of ($-$)-epicatechin did not differ from that of (+)-catechin. Under the alkaline conditions, as reported by Sears *et al.*⁶ all the isomeric catechins transform themselves to catechinic acid, 6-(3',4'-dihydroxyphenyl)-7-hydroxy-2,4,9-bicyclo [3,

TABLE 1—CORRECTED PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF CATECHINS

Sl. no.	Substance	Molecular formula	M.p.	R_f^*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
					C	H
1.	(-)-Epicatechin	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	245 ^a	—	—	—
		$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$	242-44 ^b	0.65	62.585 (62.07)	4.782 (4.83)
2.	(+) -Catechin	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	96 ^a	—	—	—
			97 ^b	0.72	49.65 (49.72)	5.95 (6.07)
		$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	177 ^b	—	54.616 (55.21)	5.578 (5.52)
		$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$	177 ^a	—	—	—
3.	Quasiracemate of (-)-epicatechin and (+)-catechin:(1:1)	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	209-10 ^b	—	62.34 (62.07)	4.94 (4.83)
			178 ^b	0.85	52.192 (52.32)	5.504 (5.81)

* On Whatman filter paper No. 1 strips using lower layer of n-BuOH : AcOH : H_2O (4 : 1 : 5).
^a Refs. 2 and 3. ^b Present work.

3,1] nonatrione in oxygen-free alkaline solutions. Freudenberg and Purmann⁷ have noted the epimerisation of (+)-catechin to (+)-epicatechin in potassium carbonate solution (pH 10.2). We have found that all the catechins on prolonged heating in aqueous carbonate solutions turn to catechinic acid. The study of boiling catechins in neutral aqueous solutions is far more interesting. The course of the reaction was followed by paper chromatography and the proposed mechanism is given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Epimerisation of (-)-epicatechin in neutral solution.

This series of aqueous equilibrium can lead to racemisation at both C-2 and C-3. The *cis* isomer being thermodynamically less stable transformed into more stable *trans* isomers. The mechanism finds ample support from the fact that epicatechins are more stable in acidic pH than in alkaline pH. The various changes at different pH values are expressed in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Transformations in (-)-epicatechins at various pH values.

The mechanism of the transformation in neutral media has been given earlier. The mechanism for the transformation at slightly alkaline pH range is given in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3. Mechanism of epimerisation and formation of catechinic acid from (-)-epicatechin in alkaline pH.

The R_f values on using the lower phase of *n*-BuOH : AcOH : H₂O (4 : 1 : 5) as elution solvent for (-)-epicatechin, (+)-catechin, (±)-catechin and a quasiracemate were 0.65, 0.72, 0.74 and 0.85, respectively. The quasiracemate (C₁₅H₁₄O₆·3H₂O) is a 1 : 1 mixture of (-)-epicatechin (2R, 3R) form and (+)-catechin (2R, 3S) form. On boiling (-)-epicatechin in aqueous NaOH solutions (pH 12-13), catechinic acid is formed, whereas an aqueous solution of K₂CO₃ is more suitable for epimerization of (-)-epicatechin (2R, 3R) form to (-)-catechin (2S, 3R) form. On prolonged heating it transforms itself to thermodynamically more stable product, catechinic acid⁶. In neutral solutions (pH 7-7.5) along with epimerization there is a pronounced racemisation at both C-2 and C-3. The epimerisation of (-)-epicatechin (2R, 3R) form to (-)-catechin (2S, 3R) form and *vice versa* and the formation of catechinic acid is explained in Scheme 3. On the other hand, the process of racemisation at both C-2 and C-3 can be visualised through a series of aqueous equilibria (Scheme 1).

Quasiracemate of (-)-epicatechin (2R, 3R) form and (+)-catechin (2R, 3S) form : quasiracemate (R_f 0.85) was for the first time isolated on cooling the neutral aqueous solution of (-)-epicatechin, which had been boiled for 13 h, and its structure confirmed by a systematic study, where only stoichiometric quantities of (-)-epicatechin and (+)-catechin on crystallisation from water produced a trihydrate of quasiracemate with a sharp melting point of 178°. The same quasiracemate also separates out when (-)-epicatechin was added to a saturated aqueous solution of (±)-catechin, (-)-catechin remained in the mother liquor.

Experimental

Thermogravimetric measurements : The catechins used were pure with respective sharp melting points, and correct C, H analyses carried out in Chemistry Department, Punjabi University, Patiala. The thermoanalytical measurements were carried out in Chemistry Department, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar ; the furnace temperature was raised at the rate of $\sim 10^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$. The instrument recorded simultaneously the temperature (t) and weight (t_g) of the substance at that temperature.

Chromatographic studies : The paper chromatography was carried out on strips of Whatman filter paper No. 1, using the lower phase of n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5). The R_f values for (-)-epicatechin, (-)-catechin or (+)-catechin, (\pm)-catechin and quasiracemate were 0.65, 0.72, 0.75 and 0.85, respectively.

Epimerization of (-)-epicatechin (2R, 3R) form to (-)-catechin (2S, 3R) form and catechinic acid : The aqueous solution of (-)-epicatechin (20 g), K_2CO_3 (0.015 g) and water (15 ml) was heated on a steam bath and course of the reaction checked by paper chromatography, drawing a sample every hour. Epimerization started during the first hour, and an equilibrium was established in 3 h. Catechinic acid formation started after 4 h.

Racemization of (-)-epicatechin at both C-2 and C-3 : (-)-Epicatechin (5.0 g) was dissolved in water (100 ml) and heated in a steam bath. The samples were drawn hourly and checked by paper chromatography. The formation of both (-)-catechin and quasiracemate started in 1 h. (-)-Epicatechin was completely transformed in 13 h refluxing in water.

Quasiracemate : (A) The stoichiometric mixture of (-)-epicatechin and (+)-catechin (2.0 g each) on crystallisation from water gave a crystalline substance, m.p. 178° (Found : C, 52.192 ; H, 5.504. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. C, 52.32 ; H, 5.81%). The excess of either one was retained in the mother liquor.

(B) A solution of (\pm)-catechin (4.0 g) and (-)-epicatechin (1.0 g) in boiling water was allowed to cool. The crystals which separated out were those of quasiracemate and were identical with those obtained under (A) (R_f 0.85). The mother liquor contained (-)-catechin (R_f 0.72).

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